

UCoin: An Efficient Privacy Preserving Scheme for Cryptocurrencies

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KEYWORDS

Cryptocurrency Privacy,
Pseudonumity,
Secure Mixing,
HDC-net,
Unlinkable Transactions

ABSTRACT

In crypto currencies, the privacy of users is preserved using pseudonymity. However, it has been shown that pseudonymity does not result in anonymity if a user's transactions are linkable. This makes crypto currencies vulnerable to deanonymization attacks. The current solutions proposed in the literature suffer from at least one of the following issues: (1) requiring a trusted third-party entity, (2) poor performance, and (3) incompatible with the standard structure of crypto currencies. In this paper, we propose Unlinkable Coin (UCoin), a secure mix-based approach to address these issues. In UCoin, the link between the input (payer) and output (payee) addresses in a transaction is broken. This is done by mixing the transactions of multiple users into a single aggregated transaction in which the output addresses have been secretly shuffled. In our protocol design, we first develop HDC-net, a secure shuffling protocol that enables a group of users to anonymously publish their data. Then, we deploy the proposed HDC-net protocol in the UCoin architecture (as a mixing unit) to generate the aggregate transactions. We show that UCoin (1) does not rely on a trusted third party, (2) can mix 50 transactions in 6.3 seconds that is 18% faster than the current solutions, and (3) is fully compatible with the architecture of Crypto currencies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since their emergence in the last decade, crypto currencies (e.g., Bitcoin) have attracted a lot of attention from both academia and industry. According to the latest records, 2224 different crypto currencies have been

listed in Crypto Currency Market Capitalizations web site with \$250 billion total market cap. The main characteristic of crypto currencies that makes them popular is that unlike e-cash systems, they do not require any trusted central party to work. Instead, crypto

currencies store users' transactions in a distributed ledger known as the block chain which is publicly accessible. Use of the block chain technology also enables crypto currencies to guarantee data integrity which is absolutely critical for financial databases. The reason is that block chains are inherently immutable and completely resistant to data modification, i.e., once data is added to the ledger, it cannot be changed or deleted. Although there is a common perception that crypto currencies provide anonymous transactions, the majority of crypto currencies still struggle to guarantee anonymity for their users. In crypto currencies, users may use many different pseudonyms (e.g., Bitcoin addresses) to preserve their privacy. Thus, they believe that their transactions are anonymous. However, this is not correct because pseudonymity does not always result in anonymity. The results of some research studies show that since users' transactions are generally linkable, they can be deanonymized by using information available in the public ledger. This may make crypto currencies vulnerable to deanonymization attacks. To address this issue, a number of privacy protection schemes have been proposed in the literature. In some of these proposals, a new crypto currency has been proposed that provides anonymity by design. In other proposed solutions, privacy-preserving protocols have been developed specially for Bitcoin to provide anonymity for its users. There are also some centralized mixing services that have been implemented to provide anonymity for Bitcoin users. They receive Bitcoin transactions from different users and mix them together into an aggregated transaction in such a way that it is infeasible to link each bitcoin address (pseudonym) in the aggregated transaction to its owner. However, these solutions suffer from at least one of the following issues: (1) requiring a trusted third-party entity, (2) poor performance (in terms of speed or storage), and (3) lack of compatibility with the standard structure of crypto currencies. Moreover, some of these proposals are vulnerable to DoS attacks or do not support block chain pruning. The latest approach (mixing services) also needs relying on a third party that is not always secure. Motivated by this, we present UCoin, an efficient protocol for anonymous payment in crypto currencies. Our protocol design consists of two phases, i.e. (1) development of a mixing protocol, and (2) integration of the mixing protocol into the architecture of crypto

currencies. In the first phase, we modify the Dining Cryptographers Network protocol (DC-net) and propose Harmonized DC-net (HDC-net) as a new decentralized and self-organizing mixing protocol. The original DC-net protocol suffers from two drawbacks that make it impractical, (1) collision possibility, and (2) security issues. We propose a solution for each drawback and develop the final HDC-net mixing protocol. HDC-net is a distributed and non-interactive mixing protocol. It enables N peers to mix their messages in such a way that an attacker who monitors the peers' traffic cannot determine which message belongs to which peer (note that message here refers to any sort of information, not necessarily payment information. In other words, HDC-net can work with non-monetary applications as well). The main characteristic of HDC-net protocol is that it does not require any trusted third party for mixing, such as a mix server or an onion router. In other solutions for anonymous communication (e.g. Tor and onion routing), a number of trusted mixing servers are needed, otherwise, the protocols become vulnerable against traffic analysis attacks [16]. In the next phase, we employ the proposed HDC-net protocol as the core module of UCoin and use it to mix the individual transactions of a group of users into a single aggregated transaction in such a way that the link between the payers and payees is unknown to any observer. We apply the proposed mechanism on Bitcoin as the most popular crypto currency to provide anonymous Bitcoin payments. The same approach can be used for other crypto currencies since our HDC-net protocol is fully-independent of the applied crypto currency settings. Using the UCoin protocol, N peers can non-interactively mix their transactions into a single aggregated transaction (without using a third-party mixing server) to ensure that the input and output accounts in the aggregated transaction are unlikable.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

In this section, we present a brief literature review of anonymity and privacy in crypto currencies. We review the related research work in three main categories (1) Crypto currencies that provide anonymity by design: A number of crypto currencies have been proposed in the literature that inherently provides anonymity for users, i.e. privacy preserving issues have been considered in their design. In CryptoNote, ring signatures are used to

group the users' addresses. The users in the group employ non-interactive zero-knowledge proofs to generate a ring signature. To verify this ring signature, all the public keys of the users in the group are required. Thus, it is not feasible to determine which address belongs to a specific user. However, in CryptoNote, a larger group size results in a transaction with a larger size. In Zerocoin, the link between transactions is hidden using non-interactive zero-knowledge Proofs. It works based on a decentralized setting, thus, it does not require any trusted party. The Schnorr technique is used for the zero-knowledge proofs. However, Zerocoin does not hide amounts and destinations of payments. To address these issues, Ben-Sasson et al. proposed Zerocash, a fully-developed ledger-based cryptocurrency. In Zerocash, Zero Knowledge Succinct Non-interactive Arguments of Knowledge (zk-SNARK) is employed to hide not only inputs but also outputs and amount of a transaction. Due to the use of zkSNARKS, Zerocash needs a one-time parameter setup performed by a trusted party. This makes it dependant on a trusted party. (2) Privacy-preserving protocols developed for Bitcoin: These protocols are added as an extension to the Bitcoin architecture to provide anonymity for the users. CoinShuffle++ proposed by Ruffing et al. is a decentralized

mixing protocol designed for Bitcoin users specifically. Coin Shuffle++ works based on DiceMix, a peer-to-peer mixing protocol proposed in the same paper. In fact, DiceMix is applied on Bitcoin to make transactions unlinkable. Coin Shuffle++ is simpler and more efficient than its predecessor, CoinShuffle. In CoinParty, a number of peers are selected to perform as mixing peers to provide unlinkability for the Bitcoin transactions. It uses threshold variant of the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) to aggregate coins by a threshold transaction in the commitment phase before the final address shuffling is performed. SecureCoin is another privacy preserving protocol that is fully compatible with Bitcoin. It shuffles the destination addresses of Bitcoin transactions using public key encryption. The employed technique is similar to the onion routing protocol. Unlike CoinParty, SecureCoin does not require any mixing peer. Thus, it is not vulnerable to disruptions that may be conducted by mixing peers. However, SecureCoin needs its users to trust the protocol since it requires the peers to deposit

their coins in a temporary aggregation bitcoin address before the main stage of the protocol is performed. (3) Mixing Services: A number of centralized mixing services have been proposed to provide anonymity for Bitcoin users. By using these services, users can send their coins to a trusted mixing service and receive them back at a new address. In fact, a mixing service removes the link between a bitcoin address used in a transaction from the owner of the transaction. However, users must fully trust the mixing service provider. These services provide limited anonymity because the mixing service provider is still able to link the new addresses to the real addresses. Mixcoin proposed by Bonneau et al. is a centralized mixing service that tries to address the first issue by using an accountable mechanism. It makes the mixing service provider accountable and ensures that any dishonest mixing operation results in poor reputation. However, it does not guarantee that the mix service always performs the protocol honestly. To enhance the Mixcoin protocol, Valenta et al. proposed Blindcoin. It uses a blind signature scheme [33] to prevent the mixing server from accessing the output addresses of transactions. Thus, the link between input and output addresses is removed for the mixing server. However, the risk of coin theft is still present.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

In this section, we present a brief literature review of anonymity and privacy in crypto currencies. We review the related research work in three main categories. (1) Crypto currencies that provide anonymity by design: A number of crypto currencies have been proposed in the literature that inherently provides anonymity for users, i.e. privacy preserving issues have been considered in their design.

In Crypto Note, ring signatures are used to group the users' addresses. The users in the group employ non-interactive zero-knowledge proofs to generate a ring signature. To verify this ring signature, all the public keys of the users in the group are required. Thus, it is not feasible to determine which address belongs to a specific user. However, in Crypto Note, a larger group size results in a transaction with a larger size. In Zerocoin, the link between transactions are hidden using non-interactive zero-knowledge Proofs. It works based on a decentralized setting, thus, it does not require any

trusted party. The Schnorr technique is used for the zero-knowledge proofs. However, Zerocoin does not hide amounts and destinations of payments. To address these issues, Ben-Sasson et al. proposed Zerocash, a fully-developed ledger-based crypto currency. In Zerocash, Zero Knowledge Succinct Non-interactive Arguments of Knowledge (zk-SNARK) is employed to hide not only inputs but also outputs and amount of a transaction. Due to the use of zkSNARKS, Zero cash needs a one-time parameter setup performed by a trusted party. This makes it dependant on a trusted party.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system we develop solutions to address the security drawbacks of the original DC-net protocol. These drawbacks make it feasible for an adversary to deanonymize the sender of each message. We propose HDC-net, a decentralized and self-organizing anonymous mixing protocol that does not require any trusted-third party. It enables a group of peers to anonymously and securely mix their messages such that it is not feasible to determine which message belongs to which peer. Further, we develop UCoin by deploying the proposed HDC-net protocol as the mix approach to provide anonymous Bitcoin payments. UCoin is simpler and faster than the current solutions. Moreover, it is fully compatible with the Bitcoin protocol.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 4.1: System Architecture

5. UML DIAGRAMS

1. CLASS DIAGRAM

The cornerstone of event-driven data exploration is the class outline. Both broad practical verification of the

application's precision and fine-grained demonstration of the model translation into software code rely on its availability. Class graphs are another data visualization option. The core components, application involvement, and class changes are all represented by comparable classes in the class diagram. Classes with three-participant boxes are referred to be "incorporated into the framework," and each class has three different locations:

- The techniques or actions that the class may use or reject are depicted at the bottom.

Fig 5.1 shows the class diagram

2. USECASE DIAGRAM:

A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

Fig 5.2 Shows the Use case Diagram

3. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams, event scenarios, and timing diagrams.

Fig 5.3 Shows the Sequence Diagram

6. RESULTS

6.1 Output Screens

Fig 6.1 User Login Page

In above screen shows the Login page of the User.

Fig 6.2 Upload the Dataset

In above screen shows the upload the dataset.

Fig 6.3 Generating the Hash Code

In above screen shows the generation of hash code.

Fig 6.4 View all the Datasets

In above screen show all the available datasets.

Fig 6.5 Server Home Page

In above screen shows the server home page.

Fig 6.6 View Cryptocurrency transaction Results in Bar Chart

In above screen shows the Cryptocurrency transaction result in bar chart.

Fig 6.7 View Cryptocurrency transaction type Results in Bar Chart

In above screen shows the Cryptocurrency transaction type results in bar chart.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed Un linkable Coin (UCoin), a secure and efficient mixing approach to protect cryptocurrencies against de anonymization attacks. It enables users to make anonymous payments by generating unlikable transactions. To develop the UCoin protocol, we first proposed HDC-net a decentralized mixing protocol that enables a group of peers to anonymously mix their messages. Then, we added HDC-net as an extension to the Bitcoin architecture to provide anonymous Bitcoin payments. The main strengths of the proposed scheme are: (1) no dependency on a trusted third-party entity, (2) fully compatible with architecture of the current crypto currencies, and (3) simpler and faster than the current solutions. Our prototype implementation shows that UCoin is a practical protocol that provides anonymity for Bitcoin users. An interesting direction for future work is to apply our HDC-net mixing protocol to other applications in which lack of anonymity is a concern. This results in developing different applications that provide anonymity as a feature for their users.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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